

The Multifaceted Pharmacological Profile of *Asteracantha longifolia* Nees: A Natural Healer

Sayali Bait¹, Preeti Hulaswar^{*2}, Sanketa Tikale³, Yogita Nimbalkar⁴,
Nandkishor Patil⁵

^{1, 3, 4, 5} Student, Y. D. Mane Institute of Pharmacy Kagal, Kolhapur.

² Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry, Y. D. Mane Institute of Pharmacy Kagal, Kolhapur

ABSTRACT

Asteracantha longifolia Nees, belonging to the family *Acanthaceae*, is an important medicinal herb used in traditional Ayurvedic and Unani systems. The plant exhibits a broad spectrum of pharmacological activities including antitumor, antirheumatic, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antioxidant, antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, erythropoietic, and fertility-enhancing effects. Phytochemical studies reveal the presence of lupeol, sitosterol, betulin, flavonoids, terpenoids, and alkaloids, which are responsible for these bioactivities. Experimental studies in animal models have confirmed its efficacy against chemically induced carcinogenesis, hepatic injury, inflammation, and hyperglycemia. The methanolic and ethanolic extracts of the plant show significant biological potential, supporting its traditional therapeutic use. This review highlights the pharmacognostical, phytochemical, and pharmacological aspects of *A. longifolia*, emphasizing its role as a natural source for drug development against various diseases.

Keywords: *Asteracantha longifolia*, antirheumatic, antidiabetic, anti-cancer, erythropoietic, hepatoprotective, male fertility

INTRODUCTION

The plant *Asteracantha longifolia nees* In Bangladeshi traditional medicine, is used orally to treat a number of conditions, including rheumatism, inflammation, jaundice, hepatic obstruction, and pain, though its effectiveness has not been scientifically proven. It is utilized in the “Rasayana,” a unique class of medications found in the Ayurvedic medical system of India. The term Rasayana It is made up of the words “Rasa,” which means elixir, and “Ayana,” which means house. Thus, the term refers to the characteristic of the plant that aids in system renewal. Numerous plants have been widely used in Ayurveda as “Rasayana” medications to treat neurodegenerative illnesses as well as tonics, immunomodulators, rejuvenators, and aphrodisiacs. [1]It is used to treat a number of ailments, such as Premeham (diabetes) and Athisaram (dysentery), and is arranged in the ayurvedic pharmaceutical arrangement as

Seethaveryam and Mathuravipaka. Phytochemical analyses of various plant extracts for the presence of sterols, triterpenes, alkaloids, flavonoids, and other compounds. Its antitumor, antimicrobial, free radical scavenging, antidiabetic, anthelmintic, and hepatoprotective properties have been demonstrated by pharmacological studies. [2][17]Several herbs have been identified as potentially helpful in the treatment of liver disorders in Sri Lankan traditional ayurvedic medicine. India and Sri Lanka are home to *Asteracantha longifolia* Linn (*Acanthaceae*), also referred to as “Neeramulliya.” [3]Spiny and 2-4 feet tall, *Asteracantha longifolia* grows in damp areas of Ceylon and India. Its seeds produce a lot of resilient mucilage when they are wet. [7]

1.1. Synonyms:

Hygrophila spinosa T. Anders and *Hygrophila auriculata* (Schumach.) Heine

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Graphical abstract: Pharmacological profile of *Asteracantha Longifolia Nees*

1.2. Vernacular names:

Iksura in Sanskrit, Kuliya khara in Bengali, Ekharo in Gujarati, Talmakhana in Hindi, Nirmuli in Malayalam, Talmakhana in Marathi, Golmidi in Tamil, and Talmakhana in Urdu.

1.3. Geographical sources:

The plant is found in large quantities in Nepal, Malaysia, Burma, Sri Lanka, and India.

1.4. Chemical components:

The herb contains chemical constituents like lupeol and sitosterol, both of which have hepatoprotective and antipyretic properties. The plant has betulin, terpenoids, steroids, and flavonoids. The plant's roots contain a phytosterol essential oil. Diuretic

characteristics. The seeds contain a lot of mucilage and potassium salts, and they also contain a yellow semi-drying oil that makes up 23% of the seeds. From the seeds, diastase, lipase, protease, and an alkaloid were identified. The seeds were also used to isolate Asterol I, II, III, and IV, Asteracanthine, and Asteracanthicine. Additionally, lupeol and an alkaloid were extracted from the entire plant. [4] [7]

1.5. Taxonomical information:

- Kingdom: *Plantae*
- Division: *Angiospermae*
- Class: *Equisetopsida* C. Agardh
- Order: *Personales*
- Family: *Acanthaceae*
- Genus: *Asteracantha*
- Species: *Asteracantha longifolia*

Figure No.01: *Asteracantha Longifolia Nees* (1. Whole plant 2. Roots 3. Flowers 4. Leaves 5.Stem 6.Seeds)

2. PHARMACOLOGICAL PROFILE:

2.1. Antitumor action:

The multi-step process of carcinogenesis has been divided into stages of initiation, promotion, and progression; each stage most likely involves both genetic and epigenetic modifications. *A. Longifolia* seed methanolic extract is used to prevent chemically induced hepatocarcinogenesis in rats.

- Animal: male Wister rat
- Part: whole plant or seeds (methanolic extract)
- Dose: 200 and 400 mg / kg of body weight

When compared to treated control valves, the administration of extract at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg body weight, followed by 2-AAF in the diet and pH, resulted in a 78% and 125% inhibition of the rate of DNA synthesis, respectively. [6]

2.2. Antirheumatic Activity:

- Parts used: whole plant

According to Amavatham, rheumatoid arthritis is a “metabolic disease.” Waste products are created at

every stage of the tissue’s transformation (dhatuParinam), and if the body does not get rid of them, the metabolites build up and lead to illness. The diastase, lipase, protease, and other enzymes found in *Asteracantha longifolia* may aid in the elimination of waste, thereby lowering stiffness, pain, and swelling. [7]

2.3. Antimicrobial activity

- Part used: whole plant (methanolic extract)
- Dose: 20mg/ml

The antimicrobial and cytotoxic properties of *Asteracantha longifolia*’s methanolic extract were investigated. The disc diffusion method was used to assess the crude extracts’ antibacterial and antifungal properties against four Gram-positive bacteria, seven Gram-negative bacteria, and seven fungi. As standards against bacteria and fungi, respectively, ciprofloxacin and fluconazole were employed. Antimicrobial properties of *A. longifolia* extracts Test tubes filled with sterile nutrient broth medium were inoculated with the test bacteria—*S. aureus*, *E. faecalis*, *K. pneumoniae*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *Escherichia coli*—and incubated for twenty-four

hours at 37°C. Sterile cotton swabs were used to aseptically swab the broth cultures on sterile nutrient agar plates. Using a sterile cork borer, wells measuring 6 mm in diameter were drilled into the inoculated plates. Labeled wells were filled with 100µl of extracts (20 mg/ml of 25% Dimethyl Sulfoxide), standard (Streptomycin, 1 mg/ml), and DMSO (25%). The zone of inhibition that developed around the wells was measured after the plates were incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C while standing up straight [9].

2.4. Anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity:

- Part used: whole plant (methanolic extract)
- Animal: mice
- Dose: 100mg/kg

Mice given an ethanol extract of the whole *Asteracantha longifolia* Nees plant (family *Acanthaceae*) exhibited anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties. The analgesic activity for both central and peripheral pharmacological actions was evaluated in mice using the hotplate, formalin-induced pain, and acetic acid-induced writhing test. The anti-inflammatory effects were measured using ear swelling caused by croton oil, ear edema caused by xylene, leukocyte migration caused by carrageenan, and granuloma formation caused by cotton pellets. The reference analgesics were 100 mg/kg of ibuprofen and 10 mg/kg of tramadol. The crude ethanol extract dramatically decreased the mice's ear swelling caused by croton oil and xylene. The ethanol extract in its crude form demonstrated a notable reduction in mice's ear swelling brought on by croton oil and xylene. The weight of the granuloma caused by a cotton pellet, the pain caused by formalin, and the leukocyte migration caused by carrageenan were all moderately inhibited by the crude extract. Acetic acid-induced abdominal constrictions were significantly inhibited by the extract administered by p.o. route. Additionally, the extract exhibited mild analgesic effects on mice's hot plate pain threshold. These findings suggested that the plant might contain anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity. [12]

2.5. Anticancer activity:

- Part used: whole plant (methanolic extract)

- Animal: Rat
- Dose: 100mg/kg; 200mg/kg; 400mg/kg

Rats' DMBA-induced mammary carcinogenesis was effectively inhibited by the methanolic extract of *A. longifolia*. The percentage decrease in tumor size was used to gauge the activity. Comparing the three doses given to the DMBA control group, there was a significant percent decrease in tumor size. The extract's antitumor activity demonstrated a dose-dependent effect [10].

2.6. Antioxidant and Antidiabetic activity:

- Part used: whole plant (hot water extract)/ seeds /Leaves
- Animal: Rat
- Dose: 300mg/kg

According to certain studies, the total antioxidant activity of the plant's hot water extract was 317.50±3.73 µmole of ascorbic acid equivalent/mg of leaf extract and 67.7 g ascorbic acid equivalent/mg of dried plant. [11] It has been reported that the antioxidant enzymes catalase (CAT) and glutathione peroxidase (GPx) in hepatocarcinoma are improved by *Asteracantha longifolia* seeds. However, the aerial portion of this plant has not yet been the subject of any antioxidant studies or hypoglycemic activity in experimental animals. In order to verify the ethnobotanical and clinical claims of the plant, the current study was conducted to examine the impact of *Asteracantha longifolia* on the levels of antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), CAT, glutathione (GSH), GPx, glutathione S-transferase (GST), TBARS, and hydroperoxides in streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic rats. [6] In both normal and alloxan-induced diabetic rats, the effects of oral administration of an ethanolic extract of *Asteracantha longifolia* were examined with respect to blood glucose, serum insulin, and liver glycogen levels. When administered to diabetic rats at a dose of 300 mg/kg body weight, the ethanolic extract dramatically reduced blood glucose levels while raising serum insulin and hepatic glycogen levels. These findings demonstrate *Asteracantha longifolia*'s hypoglycemic action. [15]

2.7. Erythropoietic activity:

- Part used: Leaves (ethanolic extract)
- Animal: Rat
- Does: 100mg/kg; 200mg/kg

Erythrocyte count, hemoglobin count, serum iron, serum protein, and other parameters increased significantly ($P < 0.05$) after receiving ethanolic extract of *Asteracantha longifolia* intraperitoneally (i.p.) at doses of 100 mg/kg and 200 mg/kg body weight. The spectrophotometric method's estimate of the extract's iron content (622 g/50 mg) could be the cause of this effect. The hematological parameters, serum iron, and serum protein were successfully restored by an ethanolic extract of *Asteracantha longifolia*, which also normalized the microcytic (smaller in size), anisocytosis (disturbed shape), and hypochromic red blood cells. Given the presence of iron and additional components like flavonoids, terpenoids, steroids, luteol, and betulin, these findings may support the use of this plant in the treatment of iron deficiency anemia. [4]

2.8. Hepatoprotective activity:

- Animal: Rat
- Part used: root (aq.extract)/Seeds (methanolic extract)
- Dose: 200mg/kg; 400mg/kg

Rats with CCl₄-induced liver toxicity were used to test the aqueous extract of the roots' hepatoprotective properties. Alanine transaminase, aspartate transaminase (AST), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), total protein, and total bilirubin were among the liver function tests that were monitored in order to gauge the activity. Additionally, histopathological analyses were performed on hepatic tissues. Using the ferric thiocyanate (FTC) and thiobarbituric acid (TBA) techniques, the root extract's in vitro antioxidant activity was also investigated. The extract demonstrated strong antioxidant and hepatoprotective properties. The impact of giving rats a methanolic extract of *Asteracantha longifolia* (AL) seeds orally on acute liver damage brought on by acetaminophen (APAP) was examined. Aspartate transaminase, alanine transaminase, alkaline phosphatase, lactate dehydrogenase, and gamma glutamyl transferase activities, as well as the serum bilirubin level, Additionally, it was discovered that when rats were challenged with APAP, their serum and liver levels of

cholesterol, triglycerides, and free fatty acids increased. A notable decrease in tissue and serum phospholipids was also linked to this. Liver histopathology showed that these changes were avoided by pretreatment with AL extract before APAP was administered. The extract's hepatoprotective activity was suggested by the results, which suggested that it might provide protection against APAP-induced liver damage. [13] [14] The use of *Asteracantha longifolia* for the treatment of liver diseases in Sri Lanka is justified by the aqueous extract's hepatoprotective and antioxidant qualities against CCl₄- and paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicities under current experimental conditions. [3]

2.9. Improve male Fertility:

- Part used: Seeds (ethanolic extract)
- Animal: Rat
- Dose: 200 mg/kg

Sexual performance treatment with ethanolic extract had a significant impact on the sexual behavior of the animals. Treatment with ethanolic extract resulted in a dose-dependent significant reduction in both the mount latency (ML) and post-ejaculation latency time. An ethanolic extract dose of 200 mg/kg resulted in a five-fold increase in mount frequency (MF). Additionally, there was a notable reduction in ML in the animals in the treated group. When compared to the control group, the extract-treated group's sperm count significantly increased. In the extract-treated group, sperm motility and survival were enhanced. The extract had a protective effect, as evidenced by the fact that the sperm count decreased by only 27.16% in the extract-treated group and 47.05% in the control group. Thus, the findings imply that rats' spermatogenesis and sexual performance are enhanced by the ethanolic extract of *A. longifolia*. The results also appear to confirm the plant's traditional aphrodisiac use. [16]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Medicinal plants have always played a vital role in traditional healthcare systems, and *Asteracantha longifolia* Nees is one such important species widely used in Ayurveda and Unani medicine. The plant has gained great attention in modern pharmacological

research because of its rich chemical composition and diverse biological activities. Phytochemical investigations have revealed the presence of alkaloids, steroids, flavonoids, triterpenoids, and phenolic compounds, which are responsible for most of its therapeutic effects. These compounds act through multiple mechanisms, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and enzyme-modulating pathways.

The broad range of pharmacological activities reported for *A. longifolia* such as hepatoprotective, antidiabetic, antitumor, antioxidant, and fertility-enhancing effects demonstrates its multifunctional therapeutic potential. Its antioxidant constituents help neutralize free radicals and prevent oxidative stress-related damage, which plays a major role in chronic diseases like cancer, diabetes, and liver disorders. Similarly, the plant's immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory actions contribute to the relief of inflammatory conditions and rheumatism, validating its traditional use in such ailments.

Experimental studies using extracts prepared from various parts of the plant particularly seeds, roots, and leaves have shown significant pharmacological responses in animal models. These findings

scientifically justify its traditional uses as a Rasayana drug, known for rejuvenation and restoration of body balance. The plant's ability to regulate multiple physiological functions, including hepatic metabolism, blood glucose control, erythropoiesis, and reproductive performance, reflects its adaptogenic and restorative nature.

However, while preclinical studies provide promising results, clinical validation is still lacking. There is a strong need for standardization of extracts, identification of active principles, and detailed studies on pharmacokinetics and toxicity. Further, the mechanisms underlying its biological effects require molecular-level investigation. Advances in modern analytical and pharmacological tools can help establish a scientific basis for its safe and effective use in modern medicine.

Overall, the available research suggests that *Asteracantha longifolia* is not only a traditional herbal remedy but also a valuable source of bioactive compounds with significant pharmacological potential. Its inclusion in modern therapeutic formulations could open new opportunities in natural drug discovery and development.

Table 1: Parts of *Asteracantha longifolia*, animal, dose and their medicinal uses

Part	Animal	Dose	Medicinal uses
Seeds/ whole plant	Male wistard rat	200mg/kg 400mg/kg	Antitumor
Whole plant	-	-	Antirheumatic
Whole plant	-	20mg/ml	Antimicrobial
Whole plant	Mice	100mg/kg	Anti-inflammatory Analgesic
Whole plant	Rat	100mg/kg 200mg/kg 400mg/kg	Anti- cancer
Seeds /Leaves/whole plant	Rat	300mg/kg	Antioxidant Antidiabetic
Root/Seeds	Rat	100mg/kg 200mg/kg	Erythropoietic
Root/ Seeds	Rat	200mg/kg 400mg/kg	Hepatoprotective
Seeds	Rat	200mg/kg	Male Fertility

Table 2 : Experimental Methods Used for Pharmacological Evaluation of *Asteracantha longifolia* Nees

Sr. No.	Activity	Methods Used	Reference No.
1	Antitumor activity	Chemically induced hepatocarcinogenesis in rats using 2-acetylaminofluorene (2-AAF); DNA synthesis inhibition assay	[6]
2	Antirheumatic activity	Evaluation based on Ayurvedic “Amavatham” model; enzyme analysis (diastase, lipase, protease) for waste elimination	[7]
3	Antimicrobial activity	Disc diffusion method using methanolic extract against Gram-positive, Gram-negative bacteria and fungi; ciprofloxacin and fluconazole as standards	[8], [9]
4	Anti-inflammatory and Analgesic activity	Croton oil- and xylene-induced ear edema, carrageenan-induced leukocyte migration, cotton pellet granuloma test, acetic acid-induced writhing, and formalin pain test in mice	[12]
5	Anticancer activity	DMBA-induced mammary carcinogenesis in Sprague Dawley rats; tumor incidence and size reduction assessment	[10]
6	Antioxidant activity	Ferric thiocyanate (FTC) and thiobarbituric acid (TBA) assays; estimation of total antioxidant capacity in ascorbic acid equivalents	[11], [13]
7	Antidiabetic activity	Streptozotocin (STZ) and alloxan-induced diabetic rat models; estimation of blood glucose, serum insulin, and liver glycogen levels	[6], [15]
8	Erythropoietic activity	Ethanol extract administered intraperitoneally; hematological analysis of hemoglobin, RBC count, serum iron, and protein levels	[4]
9	Hepatoprotective activity	CCl ₄ and paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity in rats; estimation of liver enzymes (AST, ALT, ALP, bilirubin) and histopathological examination	[13], [14], [3]
10	Male fertility enhancement	Oral administration of ethanolic seed extract in male rats; evaluation of sexual behavior parameters, sperm count, motility, and morphology	[16]

CONCLUSION:

Asteracantha longifolia Nees is a highly valued medicinal plant possessing a wide range of pharmacological properties supported by traditional claims and experimental evidence. Its diverse bioactive constituents contribute to antioxidant, hepatoprotective, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer effects, making it a promising candidate for herbal drug development. The plant has shown remarkable ability to promote health restoration, detoxification, and physiological balance, supporting its description in Ayurveda as a Rasayana herb.

Although many in vivo and in vitro studies confirm its efficacy, further research is required to isolate its active components, determine their exact mechanisms of action, and evaluate their safety in clinical settings. Standardized extract preparation and quality control

parameters should also be established for its proper therapeutic use.

In conclusion, *Asteracantha longifolia* offers immense potential as a natural source for novel pharmacological agents. With proper scientific validation and clinical exploration, it can contribute significantly to the advancement of herbal medicine and the development of safe, effective plant-based therapies.

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